

The Effect of Training on the Productivity of Workers: A case Study of National Petroleum Investment Management Service (NAPIMS)

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Abstract

Training and development are required for staff to enable them work towards taking the organization to its expected destination. It is against the backdrop of the relative importance of staff training and development in relation to organization effectiveness. Every public servant undergoes one form of training or the other in the course of their jobs. This study is aimed at finding out the effect training has on the productivity of public servant in the National Petroleum Investment Management Services. Data used for this study was collected from both primary and secondary sources. This includes the use of questionnaires, journal, textbook and publications of NAPIMS. Personal interviews were also used to collect data. Data collected was analyzed using Tables, simple percentages and chi-square. The findings revealed that training improved to large extent the performance of most workers in NAPIMS. Training improves competence of workers, updates their knowledge on their jobs, and helps them undertake certain task they could not do before training in the course of their jobs. The training received could be improved if workers were enlightened on the importance, if training was more frequent and if corporate training policy was reviewed so that it can be updated to meet current training needs.

Introduction

This research work is aimed at finding out why workers undergo various forms of training, on the course of their job. This study also seeks to identify the nature of training programs workers undergo. These programs usually have different effects on the workers. Therefore the effect of training workers and their job will be determined in the course of this project.

Training both physically, socially, intellectually and mentally are very essential in facilitating not only the level of productivity but also the development of personnel in any organization. Therefore, training can be put in a contact relevant to school administrators. However, knowledge is the ability, the skill, the understanding, the information, which every individual requires acquiring in order to be able to function effectively and perform efficiently.

In this era of rapid technological changes and globalization, increase in Productivity and efficiency of staff can only be achieved if organizations train their staff properly to enable the organization cope with the prevailing challenges. Training your employees does have a significant role in modern business era. Not just to equip them with latest tools your company has implemented, there is a lot more to it. The quality of employees and their development through training and education are major factors in determining long-term profitability of a business. If you hire and keep good employees, it is good policy to invest in the development of their skills, so they can increase their productivity.

Training often is considered for new employees only. This is a mistake because ongoing training for current employees helps them adjust to rapidly changing job

requirements. Rapid technological innovations impacting the workplace have made it necessary for people to consistently update their knowledge and skills, people have to work in multidimensional areas, which usually demand far more from their for career advancement, higher motivation and productivity.

Training and development helps to ensure that organizational members possess the knowledge and skills they need to perform their jobs effectively, take on new responsibilities, and adapt to changing conditions (Jones, George and Hill, 2000). It is further argued that training “helps improve quality, customer satisfaction, productivity, morale, management succession, business development and profitability. Until recently there has been a general resistance to investment in training in the public service because of the belief that “employees hired under a merit system must be presumed to be qualified, that they were already trained for their jobs, and that if this was not so it was evidence that initial selection of personnel was at fault. (Stahl, 1976) This assumption has been jettisoned as the need for training became obvious both in the private and the public sectors. Many organizations have come to recognize that training offers a way of “developing skills, enhancing productivity and quality of work, and building worker loyalty to the firm.

According to Garden (1973), the objective of job training is to enable an employee to perform his job in such a way as to meet the standards of output, quality, waste control, safety and other operational requirement. For the government to maximize the skills and potentials of its workers they (the workers) undergo training aimed at significantly influence their productivity and efficiency in their chosen vocation.

Significance of the study

Oil sector constitute the backbone of the economy of a great country like Nigeria; no wonder it is always the most active sector in Nigeria. It is upon this premise that government monitors the activities of the oil companies through the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation and provides the necessary infrastructures for optimum services to the public.

In spite of all efforts geared towards improving the services of the oil industry, there are some doubts as to the quality of services rendered by the oil sector to its customers in particular and the nation in general. It is in light of this that the researcher through the work intend to look into the factors militating against National Petroleum Management Service in achieving its sets objectives, by this, the study will look into the manpower base and quality of staff of the National Petroleum Management Service and assess their suitability with the aim of developing training programmes to enhance their performance since the progress of an organization is a function of the quality of those directing its affairs. The importance of this cannot be overemphasized especially in these periods when most companies are international standard complaint. It therefore behooves a company to plan and train its workers for the best quality of work to be relevant in the scheme of globalization.

Problem statement

There had been a progressive decline in the ability of manpower to cope with the challenges that attend the over unfolding new dispensation in the industry, in the circumstance, what we find is that the rise in industrial output is inconsequential in spite of the enormous wave of modern technology that now exist in industrial

activities. Most workers in the public service have undergone different forms of training at one point or the other in the course of their job. Some of these workers do not know why they are made to undergo particular training. Others go for training because of the financial benefits derives from it.

It is the opinion of industry observes that the poor performance of the organization-workers follows from their inability to keep abreast with the new technological current as a result of the absence of appropriate and sufficient staff training. It is against this background that the researcher considered the impact of performance training and development on organizational performance of this mission, however, the researcher used National Petroleum Management Service as a reference.

Research questions

1. Are the employees of the National Petroleum Management Service satisfied with quality of the selection, placement, interview procedures and promotion procedure?
2. Are there training programmes for the employees?
3. How adequate in terms of content and relevance, are these training programmes relevant?
4. Has the training process in National Petroleum Management Service improved employees' performance?
5. Are the employees of National Petroleum Management Service utilized after their training?

Objectives of the study

This research work is aimed at determining the effect of training on the productivity of public servants in NAPIMS. In order to do this effectively, the following objectives are considered: (1) To find out why workers are made to undergo training,(2) to determine what the training workers undergo seek to achieve, (3) To identify the types and nature of training of workers in public service, (4)To identify various techniques available in training of workers in the public service, (5)To find out ways to improve training outcomes.

Hypothesis of the study

The testable hypotheses of this research study are the following:

HO: There is no direct relationship between manpower training and productivity in National Petroleum Investment Management Service.

H1: There is direct relationship between the manpower training and productivity.

HO: Lack of adequate manpower training and development is not directly responsible for labour productivity

H2: Adequate manpower and development is directly responsible for higher labour productivity.

HO: Training does not significantly affect workers productivity

H3: Training significantly affects workers productivity.

Population, sample size, and sample techniques

The entire number of employees in the oil industry constitutes population of this study. The population boundary is fixed and described by the characteristics of individual members composing it as well as the nature of the variable being studied (Baridan 1990:74). The population of the study consists of existing employees, junior staff, senior staff and supervisors of NAPIMS at No 8/10 Bayo Kuku Street, Ikoyi Lagos, Nigeria. Total number of 40 questionnaires was distributed to the staff of NAPIMS. Given the fact that the relevant authorities such as the NNPC do not have reliable and current data regarding the population of employees in the oil industry. I faced a lot of difficulties of knowing the population for my chosen study. Hence the sample size used for the analysis was Forty (40).

The techniques of sampling employed in the data collection are mainly random sampling. This is adopted with the view to reducing the degree of bias and sidedness of the respondent's opinion on the topic during the personal oral interview and the distribution of the questionnaires.

Secondly, to ensure that the views of both junior, middle, supervisors and management personnel are well and adequately represented, cluster sampling techniques was used to complement the random sampling.

Data collection

The primary objective and effects of training and development in National Petroleum Investment Management Service as already elucidated upon is to impact positively effectiveness for optimum performance to achieve corporate goals of the Organization. Based on this, a questionnaire was designed to obtain the needed data. The response to the various questions is the questionnaires distributed were collected and analyzed.

Secondly, the secondary data collected were analyzed using the simple regression analysis. The data collected from the questionnaires will be presented and analyzed using tables, simple percentage and chi-square.

A total sum for forty (40) questionnaires were designed and administered to the public servants in the National Petroleum Investment Management Service (NAPIMS), only thirty (30) were returned out of which twenty-eight (28) were relevant for analysis of this research topic. And two (2) questionnaires were not relevant due to incomplete answers by the respondents they only filled some questions and they have not attend any training, this rendered them irrelevant. The questionnaires contained both open and close end questions.

Methods

The method of data analysis adopted in this study includes the simple percentage and tabular presentation of the collected data. This is because various alternative explanatory variables that are not easily quantified were used. To further test and accept or reject the formulated hypotheses, the Chi-Square distribution was employed. In this test, if the calculated values of the Chi-Square is greater than the table values at a given level of significance, the null hypotheses would be rejected and automatically accepting the alternative hypotheses and vice versa.

To ensure a high level of confidence is our test significance level of 0.0 and 0.05 were used.

Data representation and analysis:

Table 1 Distribution of Respondent by Sex

S/NO	GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Male	20	66.7
B	Female	10	33.3
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

Table 1 shows that 66.7% of the respondents are male while 33.3% are female. In summary, the table states that there is more male staff working in NAPIMS than female staff members.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status:

S/NO	MARTIAL STATUS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Single	5	16.7
B	Married	25	83.3
C	Divorced	-	-
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey 2

Comment:

From the table 2 five (5) respondents representing 16.7% of the total respondents are single while 25 respondents representing 83.3% of the total respondent are married. Out of the 16.7% of the single respondent, 15.5% are four (4) male respondents and 1.2% is one (1) female. Also out of the 83.3% of the married 76.2% sixteen (16) are male respondents while 7.1% nine (9) of them are females. In summary, the table states that there are more married workers in NAPIMS than the single workers.

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents by Age:

S/NO	AGE GROUP (YEARS)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	21-30	5	16.7
B	31-40	18	60
C	41-50	4	13.3
D	51 and above	3	10
	Total	30	100

Table 3 shows that 16.7% of the respondents are 21-30 years of age, 60% of the respondents are representing 31-40 years of age while 13.3% of the respondents are 41-50 years of age only 10% of the respondents are above 50 years of age.

In summary, the table states that workers between the ages of 31-40 are 18 in the organization, which is the highest number, and workers above 50 years of age are 3 in number while workers between 21-30 years of age are 5 in number and workers between ages 41-50 are 4 in number.

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents by Number of Years working in NAPIMS

S/NO	NUMBERS OF YEARS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	5 Years and below	4	13.3
B	6-10	3	10
C	11-15	3	10
D	16-20	13	43.4
E	Above 20	7	23.3
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

Table 4 above state that 13.3% of the respondents have worked in NAPIMS for less than 5 years, 10% of the respondents have worked for between 6-10 years and also 10% of the respondents have worked for between 11-15 years, 43.4% of the respondents have worked for 16-20 years while 23.3% have worked for more than 20 years. From this analysis 66.7% of the respondents have worked for 16 or more years in NAPIMS. This state that majority of the respondents have worked for more than 16 years in NAPIMS. In summary, the table states that most of the workers have work in NAPIMS for more than 5 years and just few of the workers have worked for 5 years and below, which means majority of the workers have working experience.

Table 5 Distribution of Respondents by Present Position

S/NO	PRESENT POSITION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Junior Staff	3	10
B	Senior Staff	13	43.4
C	Supervisor	14	46.6
D	Management staff	-	-
	Total	30	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

Table 5 shows that 10% of the respondents are junior staff members, while senior staff members accounts for 43.4% and supervisors has the highest which is 46.6% of the respondents. No management staff was available to respond to the questionnaire given out.

In summary, the table states that most of the respondents available are junior, senior and supervisors and no response from any of the management staff.

ANALYSIS OF THE RESPONDENTS OPINION ON THE RESEARCH ISSUE

Q6. Have you attended any training program?

Table 6 Training Program Attendance

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	YES	28	93.3
B	NO	2	6.7
	TOTAL	30	100

Source: Filed Survey 2015

Comment:

Table 6 shows that 93.3% of the respondents have attended one type of training program or the other 6.7% representing 2 of the respondents have not attend any training.

In summary, the table states that majority of the staff in NAPIMS have attended training programmes so we are going to use their percentage to assess this research since the aim of the research is to determine how training affects the productivity of workers.

Q7. When did you attend the last training?

Table 7 Last Training Attendance

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Less than one year ago	15	53.6
B	1-2 years	9	32.1
C	3-4 years ago	3	10.7
D	5 years ago and above	1	3.6
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

53.6% of the respondents have attended training within the last year, 32.1% of the respondents attend their last training not more than 2 years ago, 10.7% of the respondents attend their last training between 3-4 years ago, 3.6% attended their last training more than 5 years ago.

In summary, the table shows that training takes place often and more often at NAPIMS.

Q8. Is the training program relevant in your official assignment?

Table 8 Relevance of Training Program to Official Assignment

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
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A	Yes	27	96.4
B	No	1	3.6
C	Undecided	-	-
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

From table 8, 96.4% of the respondents believe that training is relevant to their official assignment while just 3.6% of the respondents felt that training is not relevant to their official assignment and none of the respondents view was undecided.

In summary, the table states that training has effect on the productivity of workers.

Q9. Are the training facilities appropriate and relevant?

Table 9 the Relevance of Appropriate Facilities

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Yes	23	82.1
B	No	4	14.3
C	Undecided	1	3.6
	Total	28	100

Source: feild survey 2015

Comment:

From table 9, 82.1% of the respondents are of the view that the training facilities used are appropriate and relevant to the type of training received.

However 14.3% of the respondents believe that the training facilities are not appropriate while another 3.6% of the respondents undecided about the relevance and appropriateness of training facilities to the type of training received.

In summary, the table states that training facilities are used appropriately and they are also relevant to the type of training workers undergo.

Q10. In your own opinion, do training programs achieve their objectives?

Table 10 Respondents opinion on Achievement of Training Objective

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUECNY	PERCENTAGE
A	Yes	19	65.2
B	No	7	27.6
C	Undecided	2	7.2
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

From table 10, 65.3% of the respondents are of the opinion that training programs achieve their objectives, 27.6% of the respondents believe that training does not

achieve their objectives, 7.1% of the respondents however are undecided if training program achieve the set objectives.

In summary, the table states that training programs achieve their main objectives.

Q11. How would you rate knowledge and skills received from training?

Table 4.11: Respondents Opinion on type of training received.

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Very high	19	65.2
B	Average/Normal	6	24
C	Poor	2	7.2
D	Undecided	1	3.6
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

Table 11, indicates that 24% of the respondents view that the knowledge training they received from training is average, 65.2% view that the knowledge Received from training is very high, while 7.2 views the knowledge is poor and 3.6% view was undecided

In summary, the table states that knowledge received by majority of the workers from training is very high.

Q12. After training are there facilities/opportunities to put training received into use?

Table 12: Respondents opinions on opportunities practicing learning outcomes.

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Yes	13	46.4
B	No	13	46.4
C	Undecided	2	7.2
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

From table 12, 46.4% of the respondents are of the view that there are facilities/opportunities provided to put the training received into use. Similarly, Another 46.4% of the respondents are of the view that there are no facilities/opportunities provided to put training received into use, 7.2% of the respondent is not sure whether facilities /opportunities are available for training received to be put in use.

In summary, the table states that there are facilities and opportunities provided to put training received into use by the workers.

Q13. Who determines the training in NAPIMS?

Table 13 Determines of training needs in NAPIMS

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	The training department	14	50
B	The staff to be trained	1	3.6
C	Supervisors of the staff	13	46.4
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

From the analysis in table 13, it can be seen that the training department and the supervisors of the staff to be trained influence greatly the training needs in NAPIMS, while a small percent (3.6%) of the staff influence the need to be trained.

From the questionnaires however, it was discovered that staff members sometimes, the training department, the staff to be trained and the supervisors of the staff to be trained altogether determine the training needs.

Q14. In your own view, what are your supervisor’s attitudes towards training?

Table 14 Determines of training needs in NAPIMS

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Positive	28	100
B	Negative	-	-
C	Undecided	-	-
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

The responses received to this question ranged from encouraging, positive, very good to seriously committed. This shows that the supervisors of most staff members have a healthy attitude towards training of the subordinates.

Q15. Does training improve your performance at work?

Table 15: Respondents opinion on how training improves work performance

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Yes	26	92.8
B	No	2	7.2
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

From table 15, 92.8% of the respondents are of the view that training improves their performance at work. However 7.2% of the respondents do not view that training enhance their performance at work.

In summary, the table states that training improves and enhances their performance at work.

Q18. Apart from training, Tick two (2) of the other factors you consider important to your productivity?

- a. Good salary
- b. Work environment
- c. Good relationship with superiors and fellow workers
- d. Provision of working aids/facilities e.g. computer etc.

Table 4.15: Respondents opinion on factors that affect productivity

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	A.B	4	14.3
B	A.C	4	14.3
C	A.D	9	32.1
D	B.C	1	3.6
E	B.D	3	10.7
F	C.D	7	25
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

From the analysis in table 4.15, at least 60% of the respondents consider good salary is important to their productivity, 28% of the respondents consider work environment important to their productivity.

About 67.8% of the respondents consider the provision of working aids/facilities like computers etc, is important to their productivity.

In summary, the table states that, it is obvious that most workers consider a good salary and provision of working aids/facilities important to their productivity, also the table shows that workers consider their working environments and relationship with superiors and fellow workers not as important as good salary and provision of working facilities in terms of their productivity at work.

Q19. Do you prefer overseas training to local training?

Table 4.16: Respondents Preferences for Overseas training to Local Training

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Yes	20	71.4
C	No	7	25
D	Undecided	1	3.6
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

From table 16, respondents representing 71.4% of the total response is prefer overseas training, while 25% of the respondents prefer local training and 3.6% of the respondents did not decide whether they prefer overseas or local Training.

In summary, the table states that most of the workers prefer overseas training to local training.

Q22. Are you satisfied with your present salary?

Table 17: Respondents Opinion on their Present Salary

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Yes	17	60.7
B	No	8	28.6
C	Undecided	3	10.7
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

From table 17, 60.7% of the respondents out of the total response are satisfied with their present salary, 28.6% are not satisfied with their present salary while 10.7% are undecided whether they are satisfied with their present salary or not.

In summary, the table states that most of the workers are satisfied with their present salary only few are not satisfied with their present salary.

Q23. Will an increase in your present pay package motivate you to work better?

Table 18: Respondents opinion on increase in pay package

S/NO	RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
A	Yes	22	78.6
B	No	2	7.1
C	Undecided	4	14.3
	Total	28	100

Source: Field Survey 2015

Comment:

Table 18, shows that majority of the respondents that is 78.6% are of the view that an increase in their present pay package will make them work better, 7.1% of the respondents hold the view that an increase in their present pay package will not make them work better while 14.3% of the respondents are undecided whether an increase in their present pay package will affect them to work or not.

In summary, the table states that increase in pay packages will increase and motivate the productivity and efficiency of the workers.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

Chi-square is used to test the stated hypothesis; the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 or 95% level of significance. The chi-square formula used is

$$X^2 = \frac{\sum (O-E)^2}{E}$$

Table 19

Observed-expected frequency table

S/NO	RESPONSES	OBS	EXP	0-E	2(0-E)	2(0-E)E
A	Yes	19	9.3	9.7	94.1	10.1
B	No	7	9.3	-2.3	5.3	0.6
C	Undecided	2	9.3	-7.3	53.3	5.7
	Total	28				16.4

X^2 + of 2 at 95% level of significances = 2.920

Decision rule

If X^2 calculated < 2 tabulated, accept H_0

If X^2 calculated > 2 tabulated, accept H_1

Since $X^2_c = 16.4$ and $X^2 = 1+$ therefore we accept H_1 , which states that training significantly improves job performance of workers.

Results

The aim of this study is to determine whether training is effective in achieving higher productivity among workers in National Petroleum Investment Management Service, other relevant areas which the study highlighted are: the reaction of the workers towards their duties when training is employed by the employer and how the managers can apply training theories of management in their attempt to direct the job behaviour of employees towards the goals of their establishment.

From the analysis, almost all NAPIMS staff have attended training within the last year, very few staff have not attend training for at least 3 years, this shows that training is regular and Often takes place

The general description of the area of study, which depicted the inevitability of training in achieving higher productivity in an organization, was stated. In the course of the study, statement of problem such as; workers leaving the organization due to poor training, their unwillingness to perform their duties well and how to motivate them to achieving desired productivity level were pointed out. To ascertain the application of the training techniques by the organization concerned and to know the problem inhibiting the success of the employees' training in the organization forms essential part of the objectives of the study. Questions relating to the objectives and problems were also looked at.

The management teams of National Petroleum Investment Management Service, together with important officers of the organization were selected as the study population with the use of simple random sampling. Both primary and secondary data were also used for this research work. The primary data was based on questionnaire while the secondary data was based on published and unpublished works. The data collected were processed and analyzed through the use of Simple percentage, Tables and Chi-square.

Scope and limitation

This research work covers the effect of training on productivity of workers in the public service. This study however, due to time and constraint and for the purpose of analysis will be restricted to workers in the National Petroleum Investment Management Service (NAPIMS), a subsidiary of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC). This research work covers the effect of training on the productivity of workers

Conclusion

From the assertions of the respondents to questions answered in the questionnaire administered to them, certain conclusions could be made.

Firstly, training is employed on regular basis. The fact that training is employed regularly shows its importance in achieving higher productivity among workers. It was also observed that its level of reliability and relevance towards productivity cannot be over-emphasized. Furthermore, its usefulness in sustaining the efficiency and effectiveness of workers in the organization further reveals its indispensability.

More so, various means of motivation such as, good remuneration, welfare services and training of staff etc has been brought into limelight that was used in the organization. On the issue of personal data in the questionnaire, it was observed that the male workers in the National Petroleum Investment Management service are more than the female counterparts. This implies that, more male are being employed than female in the organization. Conclusively, the task of using training to achieving higher productivity is worthy considering all these accruing benefits stated earlier.

Recommendations

The following are recommendations that are found useful and if rationally adopted, will go a long way in enhancing the effectiveness and the usefulness of training in achieving higher productivity in the organization. These recommendations include:

Since training is very effective towards achieving higher productivity, there is need for the management of National Petroleum Investment Management Service to regularly use it in order to benefit from its effectiveness.(1)The company should continuously embark on recruitment and training of staff in response to their needs.(2)Management of NAPIMS should consider the employment of more female staff since naturally, it will serve as motivation for the male counterpart in interacting with opposite sex, producing social liveliness that also encourage efficiency and effectiveness in an organization (3)The packages (incentives) should be enjoyed by all the workers without any discrimination and discrepancy to prevent loopholes to achieving their organization's goals.

Future studies

It would be suggested that any other researcher(s) willing to research work on this area should endeavor to get much of the opinions from middle and lower-level management who were not as busy as the top-level managers.

Conclusively, future researchers in this area of work should base their research work on all or some selected companies in the Oil Industry in order to have a wider scope of its (i.e. training) effectiveness and the Oil sector.

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